

**EFFECT OF TEAM TEACHING ON ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY AND ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE OF NCE II BIOLOGY EDUCATION STUDENTS IN FEDERAL COLLEGE OF
EDUCATION, YOLA**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology education among NCE II students at the Federal College of Education (FCE), Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The need for innovative instructional strategies to enhance learner engagement and academic outcomes in science education has become critical, particularly in teacher preparation programs where both content mastery and confidence building are essential. The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. A total of 396 NCE II Biology students were randomly assigned to two groups: an experimental group exposed to team teaching, and a control group taught using the traditional lecture method. Two researcher-developed and expert-validated instruments were used: the Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and the Biology Self-Efficacy Scale (BSES). Content validity of the instruments was established through review by experts in science education and measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the BAT was established using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), yielding a coefficient of 0.81, while the BSES was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, with a reliability index of 0.87, indicating high internal consistency. Descriptive statistics revealed that the team-taught group outperformed the traditionally-taught group in both academic performance ($M = 55.13, SD = 6.05$ vs. $M = 49.21, SD = 6.49$) and academic self-efficacy ($M = 51.56, SD = 7.55$ vs. $M = 44.51, SD = 8.06$). Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA) confirmed a statistically significant effect of the teaching method on the combined dependent variables at $p < .001$, with a partial eta squared of 0.036, reflecting a meaningful effect. The study concludes that team teaching is an effective pedagogical strategy for improving academic achievement and self-efficacy in Biology education among pre-service teachers. It recommends that colleges of education adopt and institutionalize team teaching, provide training for lecturers in team teaching models and integrate such approaches into instructional policy and planning.

Keywords: Team Teaching, Biology, Academic Performance, Academic Self-Efficacy

INTRODUCTION

Biology, a core science subject at the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) level, plays a vital role in preparing future educators with scientific literacy and pedagogical competence. It serves as a foundational discipline that equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge to understand life processes, apply scientific inquiry, and foster scientific thinking in

their future classrooms (NCCE, 2012; Olarewaju & Ogunniyi, 2020). It enables pre-service teachers to understand living systems, ecological relationships, and apply scientific methods within instructional settings. As a gateway to various scientific disciplines, Biology is essential in building a scientifically informed teacher workforce. However, despite its importance, academic performance in Biology among NCE II students at the Federal College of Education (FCE), Yola, Adamawa State, has remained persistently low (Etim, 2020; Ajayi, 2021).

Numerous factors have been implicated in the continued poor academic performance in Biology. Among these are traditional lecture-based teaching methods, inadequate use of instructional materials, large class sizes, and minimal student engagement (Ezeudu, Ofoegbu, & Anyaegbunnam, 2019). These issues are compounded by a general lack of confidence among students to tackle science-related tasks. Ahmed, Lawal, and Ahmed (2021) noted that low academic self-efficacy among pre-service teachers significantly hinders their ability to perform in science subjects like Biology. Students with low confidence are often discouraged by the abstract nature of biological concepts, leading to surface-level learning and poor achievement in examinations. The challenges are not unique to FCE Yola but are reflective of broader national trends. The Nigerian Education Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2020) reported that Biology consistently ranks among the subjects with high failure rates in NCE-level assessments across many colleges of education. This trend calls for pedagogical innovation to improve student learning outcomes and rebuild confidence in science education.

One of the innovative approaches to addressing these challenges is team teaching, a collaborative instructional method where two or more educators jointly plan, deliver, and assess lessons (Friend & Cook, 2013). This approach promotes shared expertise, diversified teaching strategies, and real-time feedback that collectively enrich the learning experience. In contrast to the one-way, lecture-dominated classroom common in many Nigerian institutions, team teaching introduces multiple perspectives, dynamic content delivery and continuous learner engagement (Onyeka, 2018). These benefits are especially useful in Biology, where visual demonstrations, practical application, and clarification of abstract content are critical to comprehension.

The effectiveness of team teaching in improving academic performance is supported by various studies. Kingdom-Aaron, Etokeren, and Okwelle (2019) found that Biology students taught through cooperative strategies involving team teaching showed significantly higher achievement and retention rates than those in traditional classrooms. Similarly, Ugwuanyi, Okeke, and Agbo (2021) reported that co-teaching methods enhanced both performance and interest in Biology among secondary and college students. The variety of teaching styles, improved class management, and collaborative instruction associated with team teaching contribute to better learning environments and higher academic achievement.

Beyond cognitive gains, team teaching also positively impacts academic self-efficacy the belief in one's capabilities to execute academic tasks successfully (Bandura, 1997). Academic self-efficacy influences students' choices, effort levels, and persistence when confronted with difficult academic material. Zimmerman (2000) emphasized that learners with high self-efficacy are more likely to embrace challenges, employ effective learning strategies, and remain motivated. In the context of FCE Yola, where many students reportedly feel overwhelmed by the complexity of Biology content, the use of team teaching can serve as a motivational tool that boosts confidence through collaborative reinforcement and multiple instructional supports.

In a recent study, Adebayo and Akinbode (2022) confirmed that students exposed to team teaching demonstrated increased confidence, reduced anxiety, and more active participation in science classrooms. By providing students with

opportunities to interact with multiple instructors who reinforce learning through repetition, inquiry, and feedback, team teaching creates a psychologically safe environment conducive to building self-efficacy.

Although Biology remains a vital subject in science education, particularly at the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) level, persistent poor academic performance among students especially in institutions like the Federal College of Education (FCE), Yola raises concern. While numerous pedagogical reforms have been suggested, the application of team teaching remains underexplored at the NCE level in Nigeria. Most studies have focused on secondary or university levels, leaving a gap in understanding how collaborative instructional models can impact pre-service teacher training in Colleges of Education (Ugwuanyi et al., 2021; Adebayo & Akinbode, 2022; Yusuf & Ajiboye, 2019).

Additionally, empirical studies focusing on Biology education in Colleges of Education are scarce, despite the complex nature of the subject which often requires diverse instructional strategies. Existing literature tends to generalize across science disciplines without disaggregating findings to reflect the unique challenges associated with teaching and learning Biology (Etim, 2020; Ajayi, 2021; Adewale & Arogundade, 2020). This limits the application of instructional solutions to subject-specific contexts.

More importantly, academic self-efficacy, a key affective domain variable that significantly predicts students' academic engagement and performance, is often neglected in studies evaluating instructional strategies (Bandura, 1997; Zimmerman, 2000). Few studies have examined how team teaching can simultaneously influence both cognitive outcomes (e.g., test scores) and affective traits such as students' belief in their ability to succeed academically (Ahmed, Lawal, & Ahmed, 2021; Ezenwosu & Nwosu, 2018).

The integration of team teaching in FCE Yola is not only timely but necessary, given the increasing demand for quality teacher education and the urgent need to reverse the trend of poor performance in science subjects. Implementing team teaching can address issues of content delivery, learner support, and classroom engagement, thus enhancing both academic self-efficacy and achievement among NCE II Biology students. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and performance in Biology education among NCE II students in FCE Yola, Adamawa State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the critical role of Biology in preparing competent science educators, many NCE II students at the Federal College of Education (FCE), Yola, continue to perform poorly in the subject. Traditional lecture methods and low levels of academic self-efficacy have been identified as major contributing factors. Innovative strategies such as team teaching which combines the strengths of multiple instructors offer promise for improving student outcomes. However, limited empirical research exists on how team teaching influences both academic performance and students' belief in their learning capabilities within this context.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

To investigate the effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology education among NCE II students in FCE Yola, Adamawa State.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among NCE II students in FCE Yola?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H₀: Team teaching has no significant effect on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among NCE II students in FCE Yola.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Team Teaching: Concept and Educational Relevance

Team teaching is a collaborative instructional strategy where two or more teachers jointly plan, deliver, and assess a course or subject (Friend & Cook, 2013). It allows educators to leverage diverse expertise, foster innovation in teaching methods, and promote professional growth. In science education, team teaching has been shown to improve conceptual understanding and student engagement (Serrano-Ibáñez et al., 2020). Recent research indicates that team teaching enhances instructional quality and provides a richer learning experience. For instance, a study by Tisdell and Thompson (2021) reported improved student participation and achievement in team-taught STEM classrooms.

Team Teaching and Academic Performance

Team teaching is positively linked to academic performance due to increased instructional support, varied pedagogical styles, and collaborative assessment. It allows educators to differentiate instruction, address students' diverse learning needs, and foster deeper understanding (Ndukwu & Obasi, 2020). A recent study by Jeong and González-Gómez (2022) found that team teaching in biology classes significantly improved test scores, particularly among students with low initial achievement levels. Furthermore, team teaching facilitates peer collaboration and critical thinking, essential for academic excellence (Murray & Ma, 2021).

Academic Self-Efficacy: Definition and Importance

Academic self-efficacy refers to students' belief in their ability to accomplish academic tasks successfully (Bandura, 1997). It plays a crucial role in learning behaviors such as persistence, goal-setting, and self-regulation (Pajares & Schunk, 2001). Recent studies reveal that students with high academic self-efficacy are more motivated and perform better in science and mathematics subjects. For example, Han et al. (2023) found that academic self-efficacy was a significant predictor of student performance in STEM disciplines.

Enhancing Academic Self-Efficacy through Team Teaching

Team teaching enhances academic self-efficacy by providing supportive learning environments and facilitating active learning. When students observe effective collaboration and receive diversified feedback from multiple teachers, their confidence in their own abilities increases (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). Moreover, collaborative learning environments have been found to improve students' self-perception of competence and increase resilience in challenging subjects such as biology (Ching et al., 2022).

Integrating Team Teaching, Academic Performance, and Self-Efficacy

There is a growing body of literature highlighting the interconnectedness of teaching strategies, academic performance, and self-efficacy. Team teaching provides cognitive and emotional scaffolding that contributes to both improved academic performance and increased student confidence (Zimmerman & Cleary, 2018). In biology education, where learners often struggle with abstract concepts, team teaching coupled with strategies that foster self-efficacy can lead to transformative academic outcomes (Olawaju & Ogunniyi, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design involving pre-test and post-test non-equivalent groups. This design was appropriate because the study involved intact classes where random assignment of participants was not feasible. Quasi-experimental designs are widely accepted in educational research where real-world classroom settings make randomization difficult (Creswell & Creswell, 2022; Johnson & Christensen, 2021). It also allows for valid comparison of outcomes before and after an intervention across different groups (Basitere, Ivala, & Mhlongo, 2021).

The population comprised all NCE II Biology students in the School of Sciences at the Federal College of Education, Yola. From this population, two intact classes were selected using purposive sampling: one assigned to the experimental group (Team Teaching) and the other to the control group (Traditional Teaching), each consisting of 198 students. Purposive sampling is suitable in quasi-experimental settings to select groups based on specific characteristics relevant to the study (Etikan & Bala, 2017; Alharbi & Dodeen, 2023).

Two main instruments were used, Biology Achievement Test (BAT): A researcher-designed 50-item multiple-choice test covering major Biology topics taught during the study period. The test was validated by subject matter experts, and a pilot test yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82 using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), indicating high internal consistency. Academic Self-Efficacy Scale (ASES) was Adapted from the validated instrument developed by Bandura (2006) and modified for the context of NCE students. It contained 20 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). Cronbach's alpha for the adapted instrument was 0.87, signifying strong reliability. The use of adapted, psychometrically sound self-efficacy instruments is endorsed in recent works (Talsma, Robertson, K., Thomas, C., & Norris, 2021; Özdemir & Uzunboylu, 2022).

The intervention lasted six weeks. In the experimental group, team teaching was implemented, where two qualified lecturers collaboratively planned, delivered, and evaluated the Biology lessons. Techniques included alternating instruction, collaborative delivery and co-assessment. The control group received instruction from a single teacher using conventional methods (lecture and note-taking). Team teaching has recently been recognized for enhancing instructional delivery and learner outcomes in higher education (Ayeni & Popoola, 2022; Lin & Lee, 2020).

The Data Collection Procedure were based on week 1: Pre-test in both groups using the BAT and ASES,

Weeks 2–5: Implementation of instructional strategies (team teaching vs traditional),

Week 6: Post-test administration of BAT and ASES.

Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were used to explore initial differences. Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA) was employed to test the hypothesis and control for pre-test scores, which enhanced the validity of the results. MANCOVA is recommended when analyzing the effect of an intervention on multiple dependent variables while accounting for initial differences (Field, 2021; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2021).

RESULTS

Research Question

What is the effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among NCE II students in FCE Yola?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology

	Teaching	Mean	Std. Deviation	n
Post-Performance	Team Teaching	55.1311	6.05142	198
	Traditional	49.2068	6.48733	198
	Total	52.1689	6.93178	396
Post Self-Efficacy	Team Teaching	51.5617	7.55466	198
	Traditional	44.5077	8.06403	198
	Total	48.0347	8.56547	396

The descriptive statistics of table 1 reveal notable differences between the Team Teaching and Traditional Teaching groups in terms of both academic performance and academic self-efficacy among NCE II students in Federal College of Education, Yola. For post-test academic performance in Biology, students taught using the team teaching method had a mean score of 55.13 with a standard deviation of 6.05, whereas those in the traditional teaching group recorded a mean score of 49.21 and a standard deviation of 6.49. This shows that students exposed to team teaching performed significantly better on average than their counterparts taught through the traditional method. The approximately 6-point difference suggests that team teaching may positively enhance students’ understanding and performance in Biology.

Similarly, for academic self-efficacy, students in the team teaching group achieved a mean score of 51.56 (SD = 7.55) compared to a mean score of 44.51 (SD = 8.06) recorded by students in the traditional group. This 7-point difference indicates that students taught through team teaching not only performed better academically but also developed a stronger belief in their ability to succeed in academic tasks. The standard deviations across both variables show relatively consistent spread of scores within each group. Overall, these findings suggest that team teaching may contribute meaningfully to improving both academic outcomes and students’ confidence in their learning ability, particularly in complex subjects like Biology. However, further inferential analysis (e.g., MANCOVA) are used to determine whether these differences are statistically significant after accounting for pre-existing differences in students’ abilities.

Research Hypothesis

H₀: Team teaching has no significant effect on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among NCE II students in FCE Yola.

Table 2: Multivariate Tests effect of team teaching on academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology

Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial		Observed Power ^d	
						Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter		
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.000	.084 ^b	2.000	389.000	.920	.000	.167	.063
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	.084 ^b	2.000	389.000	.920	.000	.167	.063
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	.084 ^b	2.000	389.000	.920	.000	.167	.063
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.084 ^b	2.000	389.000	.920	.000	.167	.063
Methods	Pillai's Trace	.036	7.187 ^b	2.000	389.000	.001	.036	14.373	.933
	Wilks' Lambda	.964	7.187 ^b	2.000	389.000	.001	.036	14.373	.933
	Hotelling's Trace	.037	7.187 ^b	2.000	389.000	.001	.036	14.373	.933
	Roy's Largest Root	.037	7.187 ^b	2.000	389.000	.001	.036	14.373	.933
Pre-test	Pillai's Trace	.043	8.645 ^b	2.000	389.000	.000	.043	17.290	.968
Performance	Wilks' Lambda	.957	8.645 ^b	2.000	389.000	.000	.043	17.290	.968
	Hotelling's Trace	.044	8.645 ^b	2.000	389.000	.000	.043	17.290	.968
	Roy's Largest Root	.044	8.645 ^b	2.000	389.000	.000	.043	17.290	.968
Pre-test Self-Efficacy	Pillai's Trace	.015	2.960 ^b	2.000	389.000	.053	.015	5.921	.574
	Wilks' Lambda	.985	2.960 ^b	2.000	389.000	.053	.015	5.921	.574
	Hotelling's Trace	.015	2.960 ^b	2.000	389.000	.053	.015	5.921	.574
	Roy's Largest Root	.015	2.960 ^b	2.000	389.000	.053	.015	5.921	.574
Methods *	Pillai's Trace	.001	.138	4.000	780.000	.968	.001	.552	.079
Pre-test	Wilks' Lambda	.999	.138 ^b	4.000	778.000	.968	.001	.551	.079
Performance	Hotelling's Trace	.001	.137	4.000	776.000	.968	.001	.550	.079
* Pre-test Self-Efficacy	Roy's Largest Root	.001	.159 ^c	2.000	390.000	.853	.001	.318	.075

- a. Design: Intercept + Method + Pre- test Performance + Pre-test Self-Efficacy + Methods * Pre- test Performance * Pre-test Self-Efficacy
- b. Exact statistic
- c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.
- d. Computed using alpha = .05

The results in table 2 show that the effect of the teaching method (methods) on the combined dependent variables is statistically significant. This is supported by all multivariate test criteria (Pillai's Trace = 0.036, Wilks' Lambda = 0.964, Hotelling's Trace = 0.037, Roy's Largest Root = 0.037), with $F(2, 389) = 7.187, p = .001$. The partial eta squared value of 0.036 indicates that approximately 3.6% of the variance in the combined post-test scores is explained by the teaching method. The observed power of 0.933 suggests a high probability that the test correctly rejected the null hypothesis when it is false, confirming a reliable effect of team teaching. The pre-test performance (Pre-Performance) also shows a statistically significant multivariate effect on the post-test outcomes (Pillai's Trace = 0.043, $F(2, 389) = 8.645, p < .001$, partial eta squared = 0.043). This suggests that initial academic performance significantly influences subsequent academic outcomes and self-efficacy. In contrast, the pre-self-efficacy test scores (Pre-Self-Efficacy) do not significantly affect the combined post-test outcomes at

the .05 level (Pillai's Trace = 0.015, $F(2, 389) = 2.960$, $p = .053$). Although this result is marginally non-significant, it suggests a trend that could be meaningful with a larger sample or adjusted model.

Lastly, the three-way interaction between Group Teaching, Pre-test Performance, and Pre-Self-Efficacy test is not statistically significant (Pillai's Trace = .001, $F(4, 780) = 0.138$, $p = .968$). This indicates that the combination of these three variables does not produce a differential effect on the post-test outcomes beyond their individual contributions.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of this study underscore the significant role that team teaching plays in enhancing both academic self-efficacy and academic performance among NCE II students studying Biology at the Federal College of Education, Yola. The descriptive statistics reveal that students exposed to the team teaching method outperformed their peers in traditional classrooms, achieving higher post-test scores in both academic performance ($M = 55.13$) and academic self-efficacy ($M = 51.56$). These results suggest that team teaching creates a more engaging and supportive learning environment, which enhances students' comprehension and belief in their academic capabilities.

These findings align with recent research emphasizing the positive impact of collaborative teaching methods on student outcomes. For instance, a study by Geng, Amini, Hashim, and Zhu (2024) found that effective teaching styles significantly influence students' academic self-efficacy and engagement, highlighting the importance of instructional approaches that foster student confidence and participation. Similarly, Rayyan, Abusalim, Alshanmy, Awwad and Alghazo. (2024) demonstrated that blended learning environments, which often incorporate elements of team teaching, enhance students' self-efficacy and academic success.

The significant effect of pre-performance aligns with Bandura's (2020) social cognitive theory, which emphasizes the role of prior experience in shaping future performance. Although pre-self-efficacy was not statistically significant, the near-threshold p -value (.053) implies a potential influence, consistent with the notion those students' initial self-beliefs may become more impactful when supported by effective instructional strategies

Moreover, the multivariate analysis showed that the teaching method had a statistically significant effect on the combined dependent variables (Wilks' Lambda = 0.964, $F(2, 389) = 7.187$, $p = .001$), with a partial eta squared of 0.036, indicating a meaningful contribution of the instructional approach to learning outcomes. This corroborates the findings of Atasoy and Yalçın (2023), who reported that team innovativeness positively affects teachers' instructional practices, which in turn can enhance student learning experiences.

Further, the statistically significant effect of pre-test academic performance (Wilks' Lambda = .957, $p < .001$) indicates that prior achievement is a predictor of future performance, consistent with the findings of Emirua and Gedifew (2024), who emphasized the role of teacher self-efficacy in influencing student engagement and learning outcomes. Although pre-test self-efficacy did not reach conventional levels of significance ($p = .053$), the result neared significance, suggesting a possible trend that could become statistically meaningful with a larger sample or alternative model.

Interestingly, the three-way interaction involving teaching methods, pre-test performance, and pre-test self-efficacy was not statistically significant ($p = .968$), indicating that the benefits of team teaching are relatively uniform across different levels of prior knowledge and efficacy. This suggests that team teaching can be a universally beneficial instructional strategy, not limited by students' starting points. Similar conclusions were drawn by Yim (2023), who found that collaborative learning contexts enhance pre-service teachers' self-efficacy, regardless of their initial confidence levels.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that team teaching has a significant and positive effect on both academic self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among NCE II students at FCE Yola. The method offers a more effective alternative to traditional instructional approaches by fostering deeper comprehension and stronger academic confidence among learners. While prior academic performance significantly contributes to learning outcomes, the teaching method itself is a critical determinant of success. These results underscore the value of adopting innovative pedagogical practices in teacher education and content delivery.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the significant findings from this study it was recommended that:

1. The Federal College of Education, Yola, and similar institutions should consider institutionalizing team teaching especially in science-based courses like Biology given its demonstrated effectiveness in improving student outcomes.
2. Ongoing professional development programs should include training on team teaching methodologies to equip educators with collaborative teaching skills and promote instructional synergy.
3. Educational policymakers should revise curriculum implementation guidelines to incorporate collaborative teaching models, encouraging co-planning and co-assessment practices.
4. Future studies should explore long-term effects of team teaching on students' academic trajectories and investigate its impact across other subject areas and demographic groups, using larger and more diverse samples.
5. Schools should provide enabling environments such as joint lesson planning time, teaching aids, and administrative support to facilitate the effective implementation of team teaching strategies.

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